

Women's Access to Microcredit and Poverty Reduction: Evidence from Lapo Microfinance Bank, Ayingba, Kogi State

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Abstract

The study examined women's access to microcredit and poverty reduction: evidence from LAPO microfinance. The study used primary data collected with the aid of a questionnaire. It utilized a sample size of 275 through a simple random sampling technique. 275 copies of questionnaires were administered and distributed among women lenders and staff of LAPO Microfinance Bank. By chance, 235 copies of the questionnaire were completed and returned to the researcher. Hence, the data was analyzed based on these returned copies of questionnaires. The study used descriptive statistics of mean analysis, simple percentage and regression analysis to analyze the data, as well as Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to test the hypotheses. Based on the results, it was revealed that the independent variables such as the rate of women's access to microcredit, interest on savings of women's microcredit and microcredit duration had negative effects on the poverty rate in Nigeria. Meanwhile, interest rate on women's microcredit, microcredit participation/registration fees and microcredit initial deposit had positive effect on poverty rate among women that have access to microcredit. The study concluded that women's access to microcredit is necessary for poverty reduction, as evidenced from LAPO Microfinance Bank, Anyigba. It was, therefore, recommended that the management of LAPO Microfinance Bank should promote women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction through an increase in women's level of income, an increase in savings habit among women, increase in their standard of living. Additionally, it strengthens the financial capacity of women and addresses challenges such as; weak institution capacity, absence of a technology platform, weak capital base, and inability to recover loans in order to enhance women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction

Keywords: Microcredit, Microfinance bank, Poverty, Poverty reduction

Introduction

One of the major challenges facing Nigeria today, as in most developing countries, is the eradication of poverty. The situation is not one of low-end poverty but of mass poverty with a high level of social, political, economic, and psychological consequences that cannot be ignored (Monday & James, 2020). Hence, poverty remains a perpetual challenge for all societies and has regularly been followed by widespread efforts to provide inclusive financial systems to cater for the poor.

Today, LAPO addresses the challenges through the provision of a range of financial services in affordable conditions (Hassan, 2021). According to the Enhancing Financial Innovation and Access (EFInA) report (2021), 40.1 million of Nigeria's 96.4 million adults, representing 41.6 percent, were financially excluded. Expectedly, financial access was favourably skewed towards males. For instance, 21.4 million females, representing 42.7% of the total adult female population, were financially excluded, while 15.6 million total male adults representing 35.8% of the total male adult population were financially excluded (Yakubu, 2021).

The justifications for LAPO Microfinance Bank delve into providing financial services that are specifically suited to the needs of women. Hence, Victor (2021) noted that women dominate the informal sector in both urban and rural economics. They engage in micro-enterprises such as subsistence farming, trading, food vending, tailoring, basiccraft work and other economic activities in the informal sector. Institutional credit will assist them in scaling up their businesses, supporting their families, as well as make more contributions to the economic growth process (Wada & Sunday, 2021).

Importantly, as a woman's income-earning capacity increases, the entire household, especially children, benefits more than when a man's income increases (Felix, 2020). In seeking to improve the standard of living of poor households, LAPO prioritizes women's access to finance as an important agenda. In addition, the economic empowerment of women is vital to emancipating them globally and supporting them to negotiate their rights within the household (Usman, 2020). LAPO Microfinance Bank has maintained consistent growth in women's finance over the years. This performance could be attributed to the uncommon commitment of its staff, management, board and clients (Bode, 2020).

To this end, access to finance is critical to the economic and social empowerment of women. Sustained independent sources of income for women translate to access to education and better nutrition for their children (Moses, 2018). Enhanced financial independence grants a stronger voice in their households and communities. LAPO Microfinance Banks' prioritization of access to finance for women is premised on these facts, and it has been instrumental to the success of the institution as a foremost microfinance services provider in Nigeria (Sunday, 2019).

Successful operations of microfinance require the right persons whose needs are likely to be met by the financial institution's services. Hence, LAPO Microfinance Bank pursues the right targeting as a means of reducing the attrition rate and improving the recovery of its loans. LAPO Microfinance bank adopts an estimation tool for the selection of its service beneficiaries. In 2012, LAPO Microfinance bank further adopted Progress Out of Poverty Index (PPI) to support objective and reliable evaluation of its services. Clients are selected according to the types of services provided (group or individual borrowers) to achieve uniformity of operations as well as monitor operational costs.

Statement of the Problem

Women face huge social and economic burdens with very few societies across developing countries according equal treatment between men and women. Customs, traditional practices, and in some cases, religion ascribe a lower social status to women and this undermines the realization of their economic potential, thereby making them more vulnerable to poverty (Paul, 2021). For many developing countries Nigeria is not an exception, LAPO Microfinance continues to be considered a very important instrument for poverty reduction. The widely held assumption is that providing financial services to poor households enables them to become micro-entrepreneurs, accumulate savings, improve their income, smooth consumption, manage risks and eventually escape the vicious cycle of poverty (Daniel, 2020).

Despite LAPO Microfinance bank intervention to provide credit facilities for women towards poverty reduction, there is great controversy as regards the poverty-reducing effect of LAPO Microfinance Bank (Yakubu & Lawal, 2021). Critics argue that LAPO Microfinance has not improved incomes but has led to increased indebtedness of the poor women, even resulting in suicides in some cases (Rasheed, 2022). It is safe to say that the discourse in the literature has moved beyond the criticism that the reality is at odds with the 'purist approach to microfinance', as it is now widely accepted that microfinance is not the 'miracle' it was claimed to be (Audu, 2018).

However, the following questions will be used to guide the study of this nature:

- i. What are the effects of LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction?
- ii. What are the challenges of LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction?
- iii. What are the challenges women face in accessing microcredit from LAPO Microfinance Bank?
- iv. What are the strategies adopted by LAPO Microfinance Bank to enhance women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction?

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of women's access to microcredit on poverty reduction: evidenced by the LAPO Microfinance bank, while the specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the effects of LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction.
- ii. Identify the challenges of LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction.
- iii. Find out the challenges women face in accessing microcredit from LAPO Microfinance Bank.
- iv. Ascertain the strategies adopted by LAPO Microfinance Bank to enhance women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction in Kogi State.

Literature Review

Conceptual Literature

Concept of Microcredit

Microcredit is the provision of financial services to low-clients (below the poverty line), including the self-employed (Joanna, 2017). It generally includes savings and credit provisions (Jammeh, 2012). Microcredit refers to programs that are poverty-focused and also provide financial and business services for impoverished persons to enable them to generate income for self-employment and improved their poverty status (Felix, 2020). Microcredit is the extension of very small loans (microloans) to impoverished borrowers who typically lack collateral, steady employment, and a verifiable credit history (Emmanuel, 2019).

Micro-credit programs, according to Mushtaq (2018), extend loans to very poor people for self-employment projects that generate income for their survival, allowing them to take care of themselves and their families. Microcredit is the extension of very small loans (microloans) to impoverished borrowers who typically lack collateral, steady employment, or a verifiable credit history. Microcredit is part of microfinance, which provides a wider range of financial services, especially savings accounts, to the poor. According to Sinha (2018), microcredit refers to the provision of small loans, while microfinance emerges as appropriate where the Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs) and NGOs complement the loans with other monetary offerings inclusive of financial savings insurance.

Concept of Microfinance Bank

Microfinance bank deals with the provision of a broad range of financial services such as savings, credit, insurance and payment services to the poor or low-income group who are excluded from the normal banking sectors (Ledgerwood, 2019). Microfinance bank deals with a development approach that provides financial as well as social intermediation. Financial intermediation includes the provision of savings, credit and insurance services, while social intermediation involves organizing citizens' groups to voice their aspirations raise concerns for consideration by policymakers and develop their self-confidence (Robinson, 2015).

The World Bank defines microfinance banks as small-scale financial services primarily credit and savings provided to people who farm or fish and who operate small enterprises or microenterprises where goods are produced, recycled, repaired, or sold; who provide services; who work for wages or commissions; who gain income from renting out small amounts of land, vehicles, draft animals, or machinery and tools; and to other individuals and groups at the local levels of developing countries, both rural and urban” (Robinson, 2015).

Microfinance bank is the key concept used in assessing the effect of micro-credit on the rural economy. It is the provision of a broad array of financial services like deposits, insurance, loans, money transfers, payment services and savings to low-income households and their micro-enterprises who are left out of the formal financial sector (Ledgerwood, 2012). Microfinance deals with a development tool that grants or provides financial services and products such as very small loans, savings, micro-leasing, micro-insurance and money transfer to assist the very or exceptionally poor in expanding or establishing their businesses.

Concept of Poverty

Poverty is a global threat, plaguing both developed and developing nations, especially Nigeria, as it has devastating effects on developing nations (Adda, 2014). Poverty is the economic condition in which people lack sufficient income to obtain certain minimal levels of health services, food, housing, clothing and education, which are necessities for the standard of living” (World Bank, 2020). The various definitions/measures of poverty lead to two perspectives, which are “income poverty” and “lack of basic need poverty.” Usman (2017) viewed income poverty as occurring when an individual does not have enough money to meet a certain standard of living while lack of basic needs poverty occurs when one is unable to meet some of the basic needs such as food, shelter and clothing, as identified by United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF).

Poverty may arise from the low productivity of the households and they face financial constraints and a lack of other incentives for entrepreneurship (Adenutsi, 2019). The World Bank indicates that poverty is categorized as both absolute and relative (Misango&Ongiti 2013). When poverty is said to be absolute, it is described as a lack of resources to meet the physical needs for survival, a lack of basic security, and the absence of one or more factors that enable individuals and families to assume basic responsibilities and to enjoy fundamental rights (Ali, 2013).

In the context of this study, poverty is a state in which an individual or household is unable to meet the basic needs of life considered as minimum requirements, to sustain livelihood in the given society. Some of these basic needs include adequate food, clean water, decent shelter, health, education, transportation, work, etc. Poverty has a strong correlation with income, even though the use of income to measure poverty has been strongly disputed.

Poverty Reduction

Poverty reduction is a set of measures, both economic and humanitarian, that are intended to lift people out of poverty (Aremu, 2014). It also means all formal activities geared towards lowering the rate and prevalence of poverty in a country. Poverty reduction is a primary objective of the world that has been advocated in the Millennium Development Goals (John, 2018). The term “poverty reduction” means not simply increasing income levels but rather creating conditions in

which all humans live healthy and creative lives with sufficient food, shelter, and clothing, and they are being guaranteed freedom, dignity, self-esteem, and freedom from unfair treatment by the government and the community get to participate in the society (Hassan, 2016).

In the context of this study, poverty reduction means not simply increasing income levels but rather creating conditions in which all humans live healthy and creative lives with sufficient food, shelter, and clothing, and they are being guaranteed freedom, dignity, self-esteem, and freedom from unfair treatment by the government and the community get to participate in the society.

Theoretical Review

Credit Rationing theory is one of the notable theories of credit rationing and was propounded by Zeller (1994). According to Zeller (1994), credit rationing theory explains that the choice to use for microcredit portends that the applicant or household intends to maximize application by way of borrowing from the lender with the possibility cost of interest rate. From the delivery side of microfinance mortgage accessibility, the Credit rationing theory is applicable. The lender requests for collateral safety and booms the interest price if the demand for the loan is greater than the supply. The lender can then ration the loan and with the aid of implication, a few candidates will get hold of the full quantity or part of the quantity carried out for at the same time as others will be disillusioned when their programs are not authorized (Zeller, 1994). This may be adduced to major agent trouble (Stiglitz, & Weiss, 1980).

The development of microfinance therefore has been tailor-made toward the availability of socio-monetary services to the poor to be able to gain their intended desires (Arun et al, 2005). It is likewise believed that the basic idea in the back of the microfinance programme is to relieve poverty and on the equal time work successfully for beneficial results along with profitability. Thereby, Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) are "doing well with the aid of doing appropriate" as they render social offerings and at the same time measure profitability in their operations (Brau & Woller, 2004).

Therefore, the Credit Rationing theory was adopted as the theory that underpins this study because it provides a more credible explanation for Women's access to microcredit. It enables them to maximize and boost their financial capacity by way of borrowing from the lender (LAPO microfinance bank) with the possibility cost of interest rate. The lender requests for collateral safety and booms the interest price if the demand for the loan is greater than the supply. The lender can then ration the loan and with the aid of implication, a few candidates will get hold of the full quantity or part of the quantity carried out for at the same time as others will be disillusioned when their programs are not authorized.

2.3 Empirical Literature

Bogale (2021) examined the impact of microfinance on poverty reduction and women's

empowerment as perceived by microfinance institutions and experienced by aspiring women credit participants in Ethiopia. The study utilized primary data using a questionnaire as its instrument of data collection. A simple percentage method was used for the analysis. It was revealed that microfinance institutions (MFIs) provide opportunities for people who are living under the poverty lines, The institution particularly encouraged poor women's households and the result showed how poverty was reduced by encouraging and providing access to finance poor households. Microfinance institutions are claimed to directly affect household income by encouraging productivity, increasing diversity of production and productivity, and maximizing the utilization of the available resources.

Ademola, Adegboyegu, Oladipo and Akanbi (2021) investigated factors responsible for the low patronage of Microfinance banks by women entrepreneurs in Southwest Nigeria. The study employed Average Gross Turnover, Factor Analysis and Goodman and Kruskal's gamma statistics to evaluate the effect of Microfinance banks on the performance of women entrepreneurs and to determine the reasons for low patronage of Microfinance banks by women entrepreneurs. The result showed that a weak but positive relationship exists between Microfinance banks and the performance of women entrepreneurs. It was also observed that harsh loan recovery methods, high-interest rates, short repayment periods and high charges imposed on customers are major reasons for the low patronage of Microfinance banks by women entrepreneurs in Nigeria. It is recommended that Microfinance banks should reduce their interest rates drastically and lengthen the repayment periods to encourage women to patronize them more and to improve their performances.

Abimbola, Ayoola and Makinde (2015) examined the impact of microcredit finance on poverty alleviation in Ogun State. A well-structured questionnaire was used to collect data from one hundred and seventy-six (176) respondents through a quota sampling technique. Data obtained was analyzed using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (r) with the use of Software Package for Social Science (SPSS version 24). The result showed that there is a significant relationship between microcredit finance and poverty alleviation in Ogun State. Subsequently, recommendations were made that for poverty to be eradicated, microfinance institutions need to be more effective and increase outreach, design products to include the poorest, and any other measure needed to spread the poverty alleviation net wider, so that significant decline in poverty takes place.

Gaps in Literature

There is no research without a gap. Most of the previous studies in this area of research interest, such as Bogale (2021), Ademola, Adegboyegu, Oladipo and Akanbi (2021), Abimbola, Ayoola and Makinde (2015), focused on the effect of microcredit on poverty reduction with little attention given to the effect of women's access to microcredit on poverty reduction. The bid to fill

this gap motivated this current study to examine the business financial inclusion benefits from women's perspective. Finally, looking at the available extant studies reviewed above related to this area of research interest were carried out in other states in Nigeria without little attention given to Anyigba in Dekina LGA of Kogi State, Nigeria, as one of the business hubs of the country which is not excluded of LAPO microfinance bank activities. It's the bid to fill this gap geographically that motivated this study to limit the study to Dekina LGA of Kogi State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study of this nature employed a survey research design. The survey design was adopted because it is appropriate for academic research of this sort, which studies a fairly large population and generalizes the findings of the population. The research population comprised 867 group lending clients and 17 members of staff of LAPO Microfinance across Dekina LGA in Kogi State of Nigeria. Hence, the total population for the study is 884.

Table 3.1: Distribution of Population of the Study

S/N	Population Characteristic	Population Size
1.	Group Lending Clients	867
2.	Staff	17
Total		884

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2022

The sample size for the study is 884 and it is determined with the aid of Taro Yamane's (1967) formula. The sample size determination procedures are shown in Equation [1]

$$[1] \quad \text{Sample Size (n)} = \frac{N}{(1+Ne^2)}$$

where: n represents sample size,
N represents the total population size of households, and
e represents acceptable sample error

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Sample Size} &= \frac{884}{(1+884(0.05^2))} \\ &= \frac{884}{3.21} \\ &= 275 \\ n &= 275 \text{ (Sample Size)} \end{aligned}$$

From the above calculations, the total number of questionnaires to be distributed is 275. The breakdown is as follows in the number of copies of the questionnaire to be distributed in the three senatorial districts. The Bowley (1976) proportional allocation formula will be used.

$$N_h = \frac{n(N_h)}{N}$$

Where; N_h = group population from each stratum, n = overall sample size, and N = overall population, N_h = sample size from each stratum

Table 3.2: Distribution of Sample Size among Target Respondents in LAPO Microfinance Bank, Anyigba

Population Characteristic	Distributed Sample	Size
Group Lending Clients:	$\frac{275 \times 867}{884} =$	270
Staff:	$\frac{275 \times 17}{884} =$	5

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2022

Table 3.3: Distribution of Copies of Questionnaire

S/N	Respondents	Questionnaire distributed
1.	Group Lending Clients	270
2.	Staff	5
	Total	275

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2022

The study employed the sampling technique of stratified random sampling. This is because stratified random sampling allows the division of the population into strata whereby a simple random sampling is used to give an equal chance of selection to the member's of the population to be included in the sample.

The study used a questionnaire as a method of data collection. The data was collected from primary sources. The study used a self-administered questionnaire which comprised mainly close-ended questions to collect information on qualitative and quantitative data. Thus, this study distributed 275 copies of the questionnaire among the group lending clients and staff of LAPO Microfinance Bank.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The study employed statistical techniques, including descriptive statistics of simple percentages to explain the individual characteristics of the primary data. Rectilinear Regression Technique (RRT) was used to achieve objective one while Analysis of Variance will be used to achieve objectives three to four.

The data collected will be analyzed using four-point Likert scale method of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (UD), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD). These options are weighted as follows; Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Strongly Disagree (2), Disagree (1)

Therefore, Mean = $\frac{\sum xi}{n}$

Where $\sum$ = summation

W = Weighted Score of the option

n = Number of occurrences

$$\frac{\sum 5+4+3+2+1}{5} = \frac{15}{5} = 3.0$$

The method to be used is the Likert scale average with a mean of 3.0 as the acceptance region and vice versa.

Rectilinear Regression Analysis

In building the model for this study to achieve objective one, the ordinary least square method of rectilinear regression analysis was used. On this basis, the model for the study can thus be specified as follows; the functional form of the model is given as shown in Equation 3.1

POR=f (RWM, INL, INS, MCD, MPF, MID)----- 3.1

The models above in mathematical and stochastic forms are specified as follows:

POR= $\beta_0 + \beta_1RWM + \beta_2INL + \beta_3INS + \beta_4MCD + \beta_5MPF + \beta_6MID + \mu$ -----3.2

Where,

POR = Poverty reduction rate

RWM = Rate of women's access to microcredit

INL = Interest rate on women microcredit

- INS = Interest on savings of women microcredit
MCD = Microcredit duration
MPF = Microcredit participation/registration fees
MID = Microcredit initial deposit
 μ = Error or Stochastic term

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the statistical significance of this study and to achieve objectives three to four. Based on the decision rule, if the significance value (Sig. value) is less than 0.05 based on the rule of thumb, reject the null hypothesis while the alternative hypothesis will be accepted. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is a statistical technique that is used to check if a series of variables are statistically significant using F-distribution or F-Statistic.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Presentation of Data

A total of 275 copies of questionnaires were administered and distributed among group lenders and staff of LAPO Microfinance Bank. By chance, 235 copies of the questionnaire were completed and returned to the researcher. Hence, the data was analyzed based on these returned copies of questionnaires.

Table 4.1

Questionnaires Administered and Returned

Questionnaires administered	Total number returned	Percentage (%)
275	235	85.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 4.1 reveals that a total of 275 copies of questionnaires were administered to the respondents and a total of 235 copies of questionnaires were returned, representing 85.0% returns.

Fig 4.1: Pie Chart Showing Analysis of Administered Questionnaires

Source: Researcher's Computation using SPSS, 2022

4.2 Socio-Demographic Data Analysis

Table 2 Percentage distribution of respondents' socio-demographic characteristics

Variables		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	20 – 40	146	62.1
	41 – 50	80	34.0
	51 and above	9	3.8
	Total	235	100.0
Gender	Male	115	48.9
	Female	120	51.1
	Total	235	100.0
Education	SSCE	118	50.2
	HND/B.Sc	115	48.9
	M.Sc/P.hD	2	0.9
	Total	235	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2022

In terms of age, Table 2 shows that 146 respondents representing, 62.1%, are between 20 and 40 years old. Another 80 respondents, representing 34.0%, are between the age of 41-50 and 9 respondents representing 3.8% are 51 years and above. This shows that majority of the respondents are between 20-40 years. It was also revealed that 48.9% of the respondents were male while 51.1% were female. Also, 50.2% of the respondents were holders of SSCE, 48.9% were holders of HND/B.Sc and 0.9% had M.Sc/PhD.

Data Analysis

Table 3: Effects of LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction

Likert Scale: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Strongly Disagree (2), Disagree (1)

S/N	Effects	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Mean	Remark
1	It increases women's level of income	95 40.2%	85 36.2%	25 10.6%	20 8.5%	10 4.3%	235	4.0	Accepted
2	It increases savings habits among women	120 51.0%	70 29.8%	30 12.8%	10 4.3%	5 2.1%	235	4.3	Accepted
3	It increases the standard of living among women	120 51.0%	70 29.8%	30 12.8%	10 4.3%	5 2.1%	235	4.3	Accepted
4	It strengthens the financial capacity of women	95 40.2%	85 36.2%	25 10.6%	20 8.5%	10 4.3%	235	4.0	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The study, using mean analysis of descriptive statistics establishes the following decision rule. The decision criterion employed was to accept any statement with a mean score of 3.0 and above and reject those with less than 3.0, based on the Likert scale of 1 to 5. Based on the acceptance of items 1 to 4 in Table 4.3, it, therefore, implied that the effects of LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction include the fact it increases women's level of income, it increases savings habits among women, it increases the standard of living among women, and it strengthens the financial capacity of women.

Table 4: Challenges faced by LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction.

Likert Scale: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Strongly Disagree (2), Disagree (1)

S/N	Challenges	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Mean	Remark
1	Weak institution capacity	95 40.2%	85 36.2%	25 10.6%	20 8.5%	10 4.3%	235	4.0	Accepted
2	Absence of a technology platform	95 40.2%	85 36.2%	25 10.6%	20 8.5%	10 4.3%	235	4.0	Accepted
3	weak capital base	120 51.0%	70 29.8%	30 12.8%	10 4.3%	5 2.1%	235	4.3	Accepted
4	Inability to recover loans	120 51.0%	70 29.8%	30 12.8%	10 4.3%	5 2.1%	235	4.3	Accepted

Source: Researcher Computation, 2022

The study, using mean analysis of descriptive statistics, makes the following decision rule. The decision criterion employed was to accept any statement with a mean score of 3.0 and above and reject those with less than 3.0 based on the Likert scale of 1 to 5. For this reason, since the mean scores of all the challenges suggested in Table4 are all greater than 3.0, it, therefore, implies their acceptance. Hence, the challenges of LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction include: weak institution capacity, absence of technology platform, weak capital base, and inability to recover loans.

Table 5: Challenges women face in accessing microcredit from LAPO Microfinance Bank
Likert Scale: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Strongly Disagree (2), Disagree (1)

S/N	Challenges	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Mean	Remark
1	Harsh loan recovery methods	100 42.6%	80 34.0%	20 8.5%	25 10.6%	10 4.3%	235	4.0	Accepted
2	high interest rates,	95 40.2%	85 36.2%	25 10.6%	20 8.5%	10 4.3%	235	4.0	Accepted
3	short repayment periods	120 51.0%	70 29.8%	30 12.8%	10 4.3%	5 2.1%	235	4.3	Accepted
4	High charges imposed on women	80 34.0%	70 29.8%	35 35%	30 12.8%	20 8.5%	235	3.7	Accepted
5	Lack of timeliness in obtaining the loan in descending order of seriousness	100 42.6%	80 34.0%	20 8.5%	25 10.6%	10 4.3%	235	4.0	Accepted

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2022

The study, using mean analysis of descriptive statistics establishes the following decision rule. The decision criterion employed was to accept any statement with a mean score of 3.0 and above and reject those with less than 3.0 based on the Likert scale of 1 to 5. For this reason, since the mean scores of all the challenges in Table 5 are all greater than 3.0, it, therefore, implies their acceptance. Thus, the challenges women face in accessing microcredit from LAPO Microfinance Bank include; harsh loan recovery methods, high interest rates, short repayment periods, high charges imposed on women, and lack of timeliness in obtaining the loan in descending order of seriousness.

Table 6: Strategies adopted by LAPO Microfinance Bank to enhance women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction.

Likert Scale: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Strongly Disagree (2), Disagree (1)

S/N	Strategies	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Mean	Remark
1	Provision of financial literacy programme and micro-business training	95 40.2%	85 36.2%	25 10.6%	20 8.5%	10 4.3%	235	4.0	Accepted
2	The microfinance bank should make a firm commitment to access finance for female owners of enterprises as a strategy for achieving gender equity and inclusive development	120 51.0%	70 29.8%	30 12.8%	10 4.3%	5 2.1%	235	4.3	Accepted
3	Provision of responsive financial services	120 51.0%	70 29.8%	30 12.8%	10 4.3%	5 2.1%	235	4.3	Accepted
4	commitment to innovations and creativity	80 34.0%	70 29.8%	35 35%	30 12.8%	20 8.5%	235	3.7	Accepted
5	Provision of group lending method	120 51.0%	70 29.8%	30 12.8%	10 4.3%	5 2.1%	235	4.3	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The study, using mean analysis of descriptive statistics, establishes the following decision rule. The decision criterion employed was to accept any statement with a mean score of 3.0 and above and reject those with less than 3.0 based on the Likert scale of 1 to 5. Based on the acceptance of items 1 to 4 on Table 3, it, therefore, implied that strategies adopted by LAPO Microfinance Bank to enhance women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction include the fact that; provision of financial literacy programme and micro-business training, the microfinance bank should make firm commitment to access to finance for female owners of enterprises as a strategy for achieving gender equity and inclusive development, provision of responsive financial services, commitment to innovations and creativity, and provision of group lending method.

Rectilinear Regression Analysis

Table 7: Rectilinear Regression Result

Dependent variable: POR

Rectilinear Regression Results		
Independent Variables	Coefficient	P-value
RWM	-0.635	0.002*
INL	0.504	0.007*
INS	-0.702	0.042*
MCD	-0.532	0.030*
MPF	0.097	0.006*
MID	0.601	0.001*
Constant	0.311	0.081

Source: Researcher's Computation using SPSS, 2022

* Significant at 5% and $R^2 = 0.6223$

Tale 4.7 showed, based on the regression coefficients of the independent variables, that the rate of women's access to microcredit, interest on savings of women's microcredit and microcredit duration had negative effects on the poverty rate in Nigeria. Meanwhile interest rate on women's microcredit, microcredit participation/registration fees, and microcredit initial deposit had positive effect on poverty rate among women who have access to microcredit.

Testing of Hypotheses

Table 8: Result of Hypothesis I

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	39.88	12	3.323	7.657	.0001
Within Groups	12.14	28	0.434		
Total	52.02	40			

Table 8 shows that the significance value (0.0001) is less than 0.05. Hence, LAPO Microfinance Bank has significant effects on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction.

Table 9: Result of Hypothesis II

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	58.94	11	5.358	11.933	.0073
Within Groups	20.22	45	0.449		
Total	79.16	56			

Table 9 shows that the significance value (0.0073) is less than 0.05. Hence, there are significant challenges faced by LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction.

Table 10: Result of Hypothesis III

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	72.11	13	5.547	8.932	.0011
Within Groups	30.45	49	0.621		
Total	102.56	62			

Table 10 shows that the significance value (0.0011) is less than 0.05. Hence, there are significant challenges faced by women in accessing microcredit from LAPO Microfinance Bank.

Table 11: Result of Hypothesis IV

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	99.23	21	4.725	5.520	.0001
Within Groups	68.49	80	0.725		
Total	167.72	101			

Table 11 shows that the significance value (0.0001) is less than 0.05. Hence, there are significant strategies adopted by LAPO Microfinance Bank to enhance women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction.

Discussion of Findings

The study examined the business financial inclusion benefits from a women's perspective: a qualitative inquiry, from LAPO microfinance bank, Anyigba, Kogi State. The specific objectives were to; examine the effects of LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction, identify the challenges of LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction, find out the challenges women face in accessing microcredit from LAPO Microfinance Bank and ascertain the strategies adopted by LAPO Microfinance Bank to enhance women access to microcredit towards poverty reduction. Descriptive statistics of simple percentages and mean analysis including ANOVA and regression analysis were used as methods of data analysis. A total of 275 copies of questionnaires were administered and distributed among group lenders and staff of LAPO Microfinance Bank. By chance, 235 copies of the questionnaire were completed and returned to the researcher. Hence, the data was analyzed based on these returned copies of questionnaires.

Based on objective one, it was revealed that the effects of LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction include the fact it increases women's level of income, increases savings habits among women, increases the standard of living among women, and strengthens the financial capacity of women. Based on objective two, the challenges of LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction include weak institution capacity, absence of a technology platform, weak capital base, and inability to recover loans.

Also, based on objective three; the challenges women face in accessing microcredit from LAPO Microfinance Bank include, harsh loan recovery methods, high-interest rates, short repayment periods, high charges imposed on women and lack of timeliness in obtaining the loan in descending order of seriousness. In addition, based on objective four, strategies adopted by LAPO Microfinance Bank to enhance women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction include the fact that; provision of a financial literacy program and micro-business training, the microfinance bank should make a firm commitment to access to finance for female owners of enterprises as a strategy for achieving gender equity and inclusive development, provision of responsive financial services, commitment to innovations and creativity and provision of group lending method.

Finally, it was shown based on the regression coefficients of the independent variables that the rate of women's access to microcredit, interest on savings of women's microcredit and microcredit duration had negative effects on the poverty rate in Nigeria while interest rate on women microcredit, microcredit participation/registration fees and microcredit initial deposit had positive effect on poverty rate among women that have access to microcredit.

Also, based on the hypotheses test, it was shown that the significance value (0.0001) is less than 0.05. Hence, LAPO Microfinance Bank has significant effects on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction. It was also shown that the significance value (0.0073) is less than 0.05. Hence, there are significant challenges faced by LAPO Microfinance Bank in women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction. It also showed that the significance value (0.0011) is less than 0.05. Hence, there are significant challenges faces by women in accessing microcredit from LAPO Microfinance Bank. To this end, it showed that the significance value (0.0001) is less than 0.05. Hence, there are significant strategies adopted by LAPO Microfinance Bank to enhance women access to microcredit towards poverty reduction.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Women's access to microcredit is necessary for poverty reduction, as evidenced by LAPO microfinance bank, Dekina L.G.A., Kogi State. Based on objective one, it was concluded that the effects of LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction include the fact it increases women level of income, it increases savings habit among women, it increases the standard of living among women, and it strengthens the financial capacity of women. Based on objective two, the challenges of LAPO Microfinance Bank on women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction include: weak institution capacity, absence of technology platform, weak capital base and inability to recover loans.

Also, based on objective three, it was concluded that the challenges women face in accessing microcredit from LAPO Microfinance Bank include harsh loan recovery methods, high-interest rates, short repayment periods, high charges imposed on women, and lack of

timeliness in obtaining the loan in descending order of seriousness. Finally, it was generalized that the strategies adopted by LAPO Microfinance Bank to enhance women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction include the fact that provision of financial literacy program and micro-business training, the microfinance bank should make firm commitment to access to finance for female owners of enterprises as a strategy for achieving gender equity and inclusive development. The following recommendations were made based on the findings. These include:

- i. The management of LAPO Microfinance Bank should promote women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction through increase in women's level of income, increase in savings habit among women, increase in their standard of living which strengthens the financial capacity of women.
- ii. The management of LAPO Microfinance Bank should address challenges such as: weak institution capacity, absence of technology platform, weak capital base and inability to recover loans in order to enhance women's access to microcredit towards poverty reduction.
- iii. Furthermore, the management of LAPO Microfinance Bank should address challenges women face in accessing microcredit from LAPO Microfinance Bank such as: harsh loan recovery methods, high-interest rates, short repayment periods, high charges imposed on women, and lack of timeliness in obtaining the loan in descending order of seriousness towards poverty reduction.
- Iv. Finally, the management of LAPO Microfinance Bank should adopt strategies such as provision of financial literacy program and micro-business training, the microfinance bank should make firm commitment to access the finance for female owners of enterprises as a strategy for achieving gender equity and inclusive development to enhance women's access to microcredit for poverty reduction.

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